

Polymerase and Proofreading Exonuclease Domains of the Nuclear-encoded DNA-dependent RNA Polymerase of Plant Mitochondria

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Abstract

Mitochondria, found in all eukaryotic cells, play a crucial role in generating much needed biological energy for the cells in the form of adenosine triphosphates (ATPs). It is a semi-autonomous organelle and is partly controlled by its own genome and mostly by the nuclear imports. To replicate its own genome, it uses two DNA polymerases, viz. polymerases IA and IB which are essentially similar to the *E. coli* DNA polymerase I. The nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase (NEP) (EC 2.7.7.6) is imported from the nucleus and involves in the transcription of all mitochondrial genes. In *Arabidopsis thaliana*, the mitochondrial NEP showed 59.05% identity to the NEP of the chloroplasts, but only 28.24% identity to the T7 RNA polymerase, suggesting the NEPs of mitochondria and chloroplasts are distinctly different. However, in both the plant NEPs, the polymerase catalytic core and proofreading (PR) exonuclease domains are completely conserved. The mitochondrial NEP's catalytic core from different plant sources is remarkably conserved and is in close agreement with other RNA polymerases reported already and possesses a typical template-binding pair (-YG-), a basic catalytic amino acid (K) to initiate catalysis and a basic nucleotide selection amino acid R at -4, from the catalytic K. The catalytic metal-binding motifs are identified based on sequence similarity and site-directed mutagenesis (SDM) experiments. The PR exonuclease of the mitochondrial NEP belongs to the DEDD-superfamily of exonucleases.

Keywords: Mitochondrial transcription; Nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase; RNA polymerase active site; Proofreading exonuclease; Exonuclease active site; Mechanism of action

1 Introduction

Mitochondria are double-membrane structures found in all eukaryotic cells and harbour the mitochondrial genomic DNAs (mtDNAs) and mitochondrial plasmids. The mitochondria are of sizes ranging from 0.5 to 4 μm and usually about dozens of mtDNA copies are found in a single mitochondrion and furthermore, as a single eukaryotic cell harbours 100s of mitochondria, the total number of copies of mtDNA exceeds > 1000 copies per cell. The copy number and shape of mitochondria vary considerably in different cell types and under different physiological conditions. They generate the much needed chemical energy for cellular activities in the form of ATPs by the process of aerobic respiration and hence, known as the power house of the cells. Thus, they are essential organelles found in all eukaryotes from yeasts to animals and plants.

Plant mitochondrial genomes are large and complex as compared to animal mitochondrial genomes. For example, nearly all animal mitochondrial genomes are ~16.5 kb in length with no or a few introns and possess little non-coding DNA, whereas plant mitochondrial genomes are quite large and their sizes range from 200 to 2500 kb. For example, the model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*'s mitochondrial genome is of 3, 66,924 bp and codes for 33 proteins, 3 rRNAs and 21 tRNAs [1]. It is interesting to note that even though their genomes are much bigger in size, they do not contain significantly more genes than their animal counterparts. The larger size of plant mitochondrial genomes is mainly due to large numbers of introns, repeats and non-coding regions in their genomes. Using mostly nuclear-encoded proteins,

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mitochondria contain all of the machinery for transcribing and translating genes encoded by the mtDNA. Unlike the nucleus, a single mitochondrion possesses many copies of its own genome. For example, depending on the tissue type and age of the plant, the number of copies per mitochondrion can vary between 50 and 500 [2].

Replication of mtDNA utilizes a bacterial-like, single subunit DNA polymerases, viz. IA and IB. Thus, most plants possess two nuclear-encoded copies of the DNA polymerases, IA and IB. It is interesting to note that in all plants where localization has been examined, these enzymes are dual targeted to both mitochondria and chloroplasts [3]. Structural, phylogenetic and multiple sequence alignment (MSA) analysis of plant mitochondrial and chloroplast DNA polymerases reveal a similarity to bacterial DNA polymerase I [4,5]. mtDNAs play an important role in cytoplasmic male sterility and this property is attributed mainly to mtDNA rearrangements, causing plants to lose their ability to make pollen, a trait which is exploited by crop breeders for hybrid generation.

1.1 Transcription by Plant Mitochondrial RNA Polymerase

RNA polymerases are crucial enzymes of life as they control the gene expression at the transcription level. Therefore, understanding the structure, function, mechanism and regulation of RNA polymerases has been the primary goal of molecular biologists since its discovery. Interestingly, these polymerases are highly conserved in all kingdoms of life, from viruses to animals and plants. [6]. Whereas the DNA polymerases essentially involve in the replication and repair of genomes, the RNA polymerases are involved in transcription of genomes, i.e., involved in the flow of genetic information from DNA→RNA in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes.

Different types of RNA polymerases perform transcription in prokaryotes and eukaryotes. For example, viruses contain two types of RNA polymerases (RNAPs), viz. DNA-dependent RNAPs (DdRps) and RNA-dependent RNAPs (RdRps), which are single-subunit (SSU) types. Eubacteria and archaeobacteria employ a single type of RNA polymerase for all their transcription needs, but it is of a multi-subunit (MSU) type. However, eukaryotes use 5 different types of RNA polymerases (I-V), which are also of MSU type [6]. The chloroplast transcription in higher plants is performed by two types of RNAPs, i) plastid-encoded RNA polymerase (PEP) and ii) nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase (NEP). PEP is essentially a eubacterial-type MSU enzyme whose catalytic core subunits are encoded by the chloroplast genome itself. However, the mitochondria use only one type of RNA polymerase that is also nuclear-encoded (NEP). Both the plant NEPs are SSU enzymes which are of T7 bacteriophage-type. [7]. Three different subtypes of NEPs are reported from mitochondria and chloroplasts in plants, viz. RPOT-1, RPOT-2 and RPOT-3. The RPOT-1 and RPOT-3 are imported into mitochondria and chloroplasts, respectively, whereas the RPOT-2 has dual targeting properties and transcribes genes in both the organelles [8].

1.2 PR Functions in RNA Polymerases

Both the DNA and RNA polymerases do make mistakes during the replication/transcription processes, but rarely [9]. However, the mistakes are corrected promptly by the PR enzymes associated with or part of these polymerases. Based on the active site structures, the PR enzymes are classified into two major groups, viz. DEDD- and PHP-superfamilies. The DEDD-superfamily is the most common in biological systems. There are two types of DEDD-superfamilies: One type of DEDD-superfamily is intrinsic type and is found in the same DNA/RNA polymerase polypeptide and functions as a multifunctional enzyme (e.g.), *E. coli* DNA pol I. In the second type of DEDD-superfamily is extrinsic type and the exonuclease function is performed by a tightly associated subunit along with the polymerase subunits in a multienzyme complex system (e.g.), ϵ -subunits of bacterial DNA pols III, ExoNs in the SARS-Coronaviruses, in the PA subunits of the polymerase in human influenza viruses and T4 DNA polymerase [7,10-13]. Again, the DEDD-superfamily of PR exonuclease consists of two subfamilies, viz. DEDD(Y) and DEDD(H), depending upon whether they employ an invariant Y or a H as the proton acceptor to initiate catalysis [14].

These two superfamilies, DEDD and PHP are invariably found/associated with the DNA/RNA replicases and transcriptases to repair any error that might occur during the replication/transcription processes [15]. However, the PHP-superfamily is not that common and has been reported only from the bacterial kingdom, but also has been reported from the viral kingdom by Palanivelu, recently [11]. The PHP-superfamily is found in the bacterial replicative DNA polymerases III (intrinsic) (the DNA pols III belong to the C-family polymerases), and in bacterial DNA polymerases X. (It is interesting to note, that the A- and B-families of the replicative polymerases are found both in prokaryotes and eukaryotes, but the C-family is found only in bacterial kingdom. Whereas the A-family polymerases possess two exonuclease domains (3→5' and 5'→3' exonucleases), the B-family polymerases possess only one exonuclease domain, i.e., 3'→5' PR exonuclease) [16]. All three families of DNA polymerases are mainly involved in genome replication and repair in biological systems.

The error rates of RNAPs are very minimal and generally in the range of 10^{-4} to 10^{-6} [7] and are corrected promptly during the transcription process itself. For error corrections, the RNAPs have evolved essentially two different mechanisms (Table 1). In the MSU-RNAPs of prokaryotes, eukaryotes, and chloroplasts, which are involved mainly in the transcription of mRNAs, the PR active site is embedded within the polymerase active site itself [6,9]. However, in other SSU RNAPs, the PR activity is either found on the same polypeptide as a separate domain (multifunctional enzyme type, MFE) or with a closely associated subunit of the enzyme (multi-enzyme complex type, MEC) as discussed earlier. The mitochondrial mRNAs have no 5' caps but have poly-A tails. Table 1 shows the types of PR activities and their localization in viruses, prokaryotes, eukaryotes and organelles.

Table 1 PR activities and their localization in viruses, prokaryotes, eukaryotes and organelle RNA polymerases

RNA/DNA Pols	Source(s)	PR active site	Reference(s)
DdRps-MSU-RNAP	Prokaryotes	Intrinsic within the RNAP active site itself	[6,9]
DdRps-MSU-RNAPs	Eukaryotes		
DdRps-MSU-RNAPs	All eukaryotic (pols I-III)	Intrinsic within the RNAP active site itself	[6,9]
DdRps-MSU-RNAPs	Plants (pols IV & V)	Intrinsic within the RNAP active site itself	[6,9]
RdRps-SSU Types	(+) Strand RNA Viruses (e.g., SARS-CoVs, SARS-related CoVs, Human-CoVs)	DEDD(H)-superfamily# (In the associated ExoN subunit)	[10]
RdRps-SSU Types	(-) Strand RNA Viruses (e.g., Human Influenza Viruses A, B & C)	DEDD(H)- superfamily# (In the PA subunit of the RNA polymerase)	[11]
DdDps-SSU Type	T4 DNA pol (<i>E. coli</i> Phage)	DEDD(Y) superfamily^ (In the same polypeptide)	[12]
DdDps-SSU Type	<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I	DEDD(Y) superfamily^ (In the same polypeptide)	[13]
	<u>Plant (Chloroplasts)</u>		
DdDps-SSU Types	DNA pols IA & IB (Plant chloroplasts)	DEDD(Y) superfamily^ (In the same polypeptide)	[5]
DdRps-SSU Type	(NEP) (Plant chloroplasts)	DEDD(H) superfamily# (In the same polypeptide)	[5]
	<u>Plant (Mitochondria)</u>		
DdRps-SSU Type	RNA Pol (NEP) (Plant Mitochondria)	DEDD(H) superfamily# (In the same polypeptide, MFE)	This work

Pols, Polymerases. ^*E. coli* DNA pol I and pol II types; # Similar to the ϵ -subunit of bacterial DNA pols III (DNA replicases).

The polymerase and PR exonuclease domains in the DNA polymerases IA, IB and Nuclear-Encoded RNA Polymerase (NEP) of the plant chloroplasts and the MSU eubacterial type PEP are already discussed in detail by Palanivelu [5 and references therein], and, therefore, the polymerase and PR exonuclease domains of the NEP of plant mitochondria are analyzed and reported in this communication.

2 Material and methods

The protein sequence data of the NEPs from various plant mitochondria were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. The polymerase and PR active sites are arrived at by sequence similarities, site-directed mutagenesis (SDM) and X-ray crystallographic data from other DNA and RNA polymerases, already reported.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Analysis of Mitochondrial NEPs

Figure 1 shows the MSA of the mitochondrial NEPs from various plant sources. (Only the regions required for the discussions are shown here). The *A. thaliana* sequence is used as the reference and highlighted in yellow. The N-terminal region of ~150 amino acids is not conserved and showed many gaps in the alignment (not shown). After that, conservations are observed and a clear demarcation of the PR exonuclease domain is seen (highlighted in red). The PR exonuclease domain contains the typical DEDD-superfamily active site amino acids and is highlighted in light blue. The first conserved triad DV/I/TE of the DEDD-superfamily of exonucleases is seen after ~500 amino acids from the N-terminal. Again, after ~745 amino acids, a second demarcation in the sequences is seen and that contains the polymerase domain and the active site amino acids are highlighted in yellow. The polymerase core region is completely conserved in all NEPs from different plant sources and contains the template-binding -YG- pair, the catalytic amino acid K and the nucleotide discriminating amino acid R at -4 from the catalytic K. The active site, ⁻⁷⁴⁶VDR-⁴KLVK⁷⁵²Q¹TVMTSVY⁸GVT-, is found to be very similar to the confirmed active site of *E. coli* DNA pol I, ^{-QR-}⁴RS^{AK}⁷⁵⁸A¹IN^FGLI^Y⁸GM- [13] and in close agreement to the active sites of the other DNA/RNA polymerases already reported (Table 2) [7]. The catalytic metal-binding Ds in -HQD⁶⁷⁷- and -HD⁹⁰⁹S- motifs are highlighted in dark green. Site-directed mutagenesis data have shown that the substitutions of the Ds in -AFD⁵³⁷G- and -HD⁸¹²S motifs to D⁵³⁷→N and D⁸¹²→N resulted in the complete loss of T7 RNAP activity [17,18]. An additional -DxD- type metal-binding motif is found in this domain and highlighted in light green. All the RNA polymerases invariably end in the tetrapeptide, -YFFN- and its significance is not clear now. Interestingly, a highly conserved decapeptide, -IPYL/I/VPML/I/VPP-, is found in all the mitochondrial NEPS at the N-terminal region (highlighted) and its significance is not clear now.

3.1.1 CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of plant mitochondrial RNA polymerases (NEPs)

tr AOA816ZBA3 AOA816ZBA3_BRANA	QSSKNVTLENT-KLSRRYGCIECDPLIRKGLDKSARHMV	IPYLPMLIPP	RNWTGYDQGAH	405
sp P92969 RPOT1_ARATH	QNFRTVLENT-KTSRRYGCIECDPLVHKGLDKSARHMV	IPYLPMLIPP	QNWYDQGAH	422
tr S8EG02 S8EG02_9LAMI	HTSRTVCREK--RQTRRYGVVQCDPLVHKGLEKAARHVM	IPYMPMLVPP	NWYDYGKGGY	412
tr AOA0Q3EKS1 AOA0Q3EKS1_BRADI	HEMRTVTREQQ-KSSRRYGVIKCDPLIRQGLDRTAKHVM	IPYMPMLIPP	SWTGYDKGAH	438
tr AOA8S0QEE5 AOA8S0QEE5_OLEEU	HSLKTV--ETQ-RGSRRYGVIECDPLVRKGLERTARHVM	IPYMPMLVPP	NWYDYGKGGY	424
tr AOA0V0IXS1 AOA0V0IXS1_SOLCH	HTLKTV--ETV-KGSRRYGVIECDPLVRKGLDKTARHVM	IPYMPMLVPP	QNSWYDYGKGGY	439
NP_001312318.1	HTLKTV--ETM-KGSRRYGVIECDPLVRKGLDKTARHVM	IPYMPMLVPP	QSWLGYDKGGY	448
NP_001289502.1	HTLKTV--ETM-KGSRRYGVIECDPLVRKGLDKTARHVM	IPYMPMLVPP	QSWLGYDKGGY	448
tr AOA565CQ27 AOA565CQ27_9BRAS	HKFKTVTKYPGSRMRRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	445
tr AOA087GS25 AOA087GS25_ARAAL	HKFKTVTKYPGSKLVRRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	426
tr R0HH96 R0HH96_9BRAS	HKFKTVTKYPGSKLVRRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	437
tr AOA3P6GE78 AOA3P6GE78_BRAOL	HKFKTVTKYPGSKLVRRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	421
tr AOA078HME9 AOA078HME9_BRANA	HKFKTVTKYPGSKMRRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	419
tr AOA8S9IIZ9 AOA8S9IIZ9_BRACR	HKFKTVTKYPGSKLVRRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	422
tr AOA2G2WAZ7 AOA2G2WAZ7_CAPBA	HVFRIATRDPRKNIIVKRYGVIECDPLVIVGVDRTVKQMM	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	425
tr AOA6P6SN94 AOA6P6SN94_COFAR	HTFKIATNEAGQNPVKRYGVIVCDPVIHSGLDRSVNHMM	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	476
tr AOA445AVH3 AOA445AVH3_ARAHY	HRFKAISKNPGEKILKNYGIIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYMPMLIPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	440
tr AOA445END8 AOA445END8_ARAHY	HRFKAISKNPGEKILKNYGIIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYMPMLIPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	441
tr F6HYL3 F6HYL3_VITVI	HTFKTVTKESGQKDWRRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLIPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	425
tr AOA5N6RVV2 AOA5N6RVV2_9ROSI	HTFKPVVTPGQKIVKRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	426
tr AOA6J1KHL7 AOA6J1KHL7_CUCMA	HSFKPVAKTPGQKLVKRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	422
tr AOA6J1E061 AOA6J1E061_MOMCH	HRFKPVVTKTPGQKIVKRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	418
tr AOA0A0LH38 AOA0A0LH38_CUCSA	HGFKPVAKTPGQNFVKKYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	422
tr AOA1S3BU26 AOA1S3BU26_CUCME	HGFKPVAKTPGQNFVKKYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYVPMPLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	422
tr AOA8T3B2K3 AOA8T3B2K3_DENNO	HILKAVSVEDG-KLKNRYGVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLIPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	431
tr AOA3B6RRH2 AOA3B6RRH2_WHEAT	HVLRKPIVENG-RLKKKHFVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	395
tr AOA8I6Z6W4 AOA8I6Z6W4_HORVV	HVLRKPIVENG-RLKKKHFVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	394
tr AOA3L6DFV0 AOA3L6DFV0_MAIZE	HVLRQPIIENG-RLKKKHWVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	398
tr AOA921U2C4 AOA921U2C4_SORBI	HVLRQPIIENG-RLKKKHWVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	405
tr AOA3L6PDV3 AOA3L6PDV3_PANMI	HVLRQPIIENG-RLKKKHWVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	396
tr AOA2S3HHG5 AOA2S3HHG5_9POAL	HVLRQPIIENG-RLKKKHWVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	400
tr AOA2T7DVW7 AOA2T7DVW7_9POAL	HVLRQPIIENG-RLKKKHWVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLVPP	KRWKGYDKGGY	396
tr AOA6G1CRT5 AOA6G1CRT5_9ORYZ	HILRQPIIENG-RLKKKHWVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLVPP	KRWKGYDTGGY	256
tr AOA8J5SZQ4 AOA8J5SZQ4_ZIZPA	HVLRQPIVENG-RLKKKHWVIECDPLVLRKGLDKSARHML	IPYLPMLIPP	KRWKGYDTGGY	394
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		PR exonuclease		
tr	A0A816ZBA3 A0A816ZBA3_BRANA	FFLP	SYLMRTNGSKQRIAVNKTPKAQLEPVFKALDTLGNTKWRINKKVLSDLVDRIWANG	465
sp	P92969 RPOT1_ARATH	FFLP	SYVMRTHGAKQQRIVMKRTPEKQLEPVYEALDTLGNTKWKINKKVLSDLVDRIWANG	482
tr	S8EG02 S8EG02_9LAMI	LFLP	SQVMRTHGAKQREAVKRVPRQLYPVYEALDTLGNTGWRVNRKRVSIIVERIWGSG	472
tr	A0A0Q3EK51 A0A0Q3EK51_BRADI	LFLP	SYVMRTHGARQREAVKAPKAPKQMLIFEALDTLGSTKWRINKKVLSDIVDRIWSSG	498
tr	A0A8S0QEE5 A0A8S0QEE5_OLEEU	LFLP	SYIMRTHGAKQREAVKRVPRKQLEPVFEALNTLGTTKWKVNKRILAVIDRIWASG	484
tr	A0A0V0IXS1 A0A0V0IXS1_SOLCH	LFLP	SYIMRTHGAKQREAVKRVPRKQLEPVFQALDTLGNTKWRVNRKVLGILDRIWASG	499
NP	_001312318.1	LFLP	SYIMRTHGAKQREAVKRVPRKQLEPVFQALDTLGNTKWRVNRKVLGIVNRIWASG	508
NP	_001289502.1	LFLP	SYIMRTHGAKQREAVKRVPRKQLEPVFQALDTLGNTKWRVNRKVLGIVDRIWASG	508
tr	A0A565CQ27 A0A565CQ27_9BRAS	LFLP	SYIMRTHGSKKQDALRDVSHKTAHRVFEALDTLGNTKWRVNRKILDVVERLWADG	505
tr	A0A087GS25 A0A087GS25_ARAAL	LFLP	SYIMRTHGSKKQDALRDVSHKTAHRVFEALDTLGNTKWRVNRKILDVVERLWADG	486
tr	R0HH96 R0HH96_9BRAS	LFLP	SYIMRTHGSKKQDALRDISKTAHRVFEALDTLGNTKWRVNRKILDVVERLWADG	497
tr	A0A3P6GE78 A0A3P6GE78_BRAOL	LFLP	SYIMRTHGSKKQDALRDISKTAHRVFEALDTLGNTKWRVNRKILDVVERLWADG	481
tr	A0A078HME9 A0A078HME9_BRANA	LFLP	SYIMRTHGSKKQDALRDISKTAHRVFEALDTLGNTKWRVNRKILDVVERLWADG	479
tr	A0A8S9II29 A0A8S9II29_BRACR	LFLP	SYIMRTHGSKKQDALRDISKTAHRVFEALDTLGNTKWRVNRKILDVVERLWADG	482
tr	A0A2G2WA27 A0A2G2WA27_CAPBA	LFLP	SYLMRTHGSRQQDAVRSVSGKQMQVYEALDTLGSTKWRVNRKILSVVSEIWSGG	485
tr	A0A6P6SN94 A0A6P6SN94_COFAR	LFLP	SYLMRTHGSRQQDAIKCAPVKQMQVYEALDTLGNTKWRVNRKILSVVSEIWSGG	536
tr	A0A445AVH3 A0A445AVH3_ARAHY	LFLP	SYIMRTHGSKKQDTMKNVKTQMQKVFALDVLGSTKWRINRRLAVVEAVWAGG	500
tr	A0A445END8 A0A445END8_ARAHY	LFLP	SYIMRTHGSKKQDTLKNVKTQMQKVFALDVLGSTKWRINRRLAVVEAVWAGG	501
tr	F6HYL3 F6HYL3_VITVI	LFLP	SYVMRTHGSRQQDAVKSVPKQKVFALDVLGNTKWRINRRLVSVVSEIWSG	485
tr	A0A5N6RVV2 A0A5N6RVV2_9ROSI	LFLP	SYVMRTHGSRQQDAVKSVPKQKVFALDVLGNTKWRVNRRLNIVECIIWARG	486
tr	A0A6J1KHL7 A0A6J1KHL7_CUCMA	LFLP	SYVMRTHGSRQQDAMKNI SGKQMQKVFALDMLGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	482
tr	A0A6J1E061 A0A6J1E061_MOMCH	LFLP	SYVMRTHGSRQQDAMKNI SGKQMQKVFALDMLGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	478
tr	A0A0A0LH38 A0A0A0LH38_CUCSA	FFLP	SYVMRTHGSRQQDAMKNI SGKQMQKVFALDMLGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	482
tr	A0A1S3BU26 A0A1S3BU26_CUCME	FFLP	SYVMRTHGSRQQDAMKNI SGKQMQKVFALDMLGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	482
tr	A0A8T3B2K3 A0A8T3B2K3_DENNO	LFLP	SYVMRTHGAKDQNAIKSVPRKQLNKVFEALDTLGSTKWRVNRKILQVVTIWSG	491
tr	A0A3B6RRH2 A0A3B6RRH2_WHEAT	LFLP	SYVMRTHGSKKQDQKDAIKSVPRKQLRKVFEALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	455
tr	A0A8I6Z6W4 A0A8I6Z6W4_HORVV	LFLP	SYVMRTHGVKDKQKDAIKSVPRKQLRKVFEALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	454
tr	A0A3L6DFV0 A0A3L6DFV0_MAIZE	LFLP	SYIMRTHGVKDKDAINSVPKQKVFALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	458
tr	A0A921U2C4 A0A921U2C4_SORBI	LFLP	SYIMRTHGVKDKDAINSVPKQKVFALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	465
tr	A0A3L6PDV3 A0A3L6PDV3_PANMI	LFLP	SYIMRTHGVKDKDAINSVPKQKVFALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	456
tr	A0A2S3HHG5 A0A2S3HHG5_9POAL	LFLP	SYIMRTHGVKDKDAINSVPKQKVFALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	460
tr	A0A2T7DVW7 A0A2T7DVW7_9POAL	LFLP	SYIMRTHGVKDKDAINSVPKQKVFALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	456
tr	A0A6G1CRT5 A0A6G1CRT5_9ORYZ	LFLP	SYIMRTHGVKDKQKDAIKSVPRKQLRKVFEALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	316
tr	A0A8J5SZQ4 A0A8J5SZQ4_ZIZPA	LFLP	SYIMRTHGVKDKDAINSVPKQKVFALDILGSTKWRVNRRLVSVVSEIWSG	454
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tr	A0A816ZBA3 A0A816ZBA3_BRANA	GRGLGLVDRDVPPEEPDGEDQEELKQWKVKFEANKENSERHSQRCDIE	LKLVARKM	525
sp	P92969 RPOT1_ARATH	GRIGGLVDREDVPIPEPEREDQEKFNKRWESKKA IKQNNRHSQRCDIE	LKLVARKM	542
tr	S8EG02 S8EG02_9LAMI	GNLAGMVDNRDIAFPEQTEDETELLKWKWKVVRVKKENSEKHSRLRCDIE	LKLVARKL	532
tr	A0A0Q3EK51 A0A0Q3EK51_BRADI	GRGLADLVDRDVPPEEPDTEDETELLKWKWRNLSVKKENSERHSQRCDIE	LKLVARKM	558
tr	A0A8S0QEE5 A0A8S0QEE5_OLEEU	GQLADLVDRDVPPEEPDTEDEAEIRKWKWKVKAACKENSERHSQRCDIE	LKLVARKM	544
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tr	A0A6J1E061 A0A6J1E061_MOMCH	GNTAGLVDRDVPPEKPL-GDLTMEQEWKWSVRKAKKINQELHSQRCDIE	LKLVARKM	537
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tr A0A0V0IXS1 A0A0V0IXS1_SOLCH	FFN	993
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NP_001289502.1	FFN	1002
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A0A8S0QEE5_OLEEU <i>Olea europaea</i> ,	A0A0V0IXS1_SOLCH <i>Solanum chacoense</i>
001312318.1 RNA pol 1B, <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> ,	001289502.1 Pol1, <i>Nicotiana sylvestris</i>
A0A565CQ27_9BRAS <i>Arabis nemorensis</i> ,	A0A087GS25_ARAAL <i>Arabis alpina</i>
R0HH96_9BRAS <i>Capsella rubella</i> ,	A0A3P6GE78_BRAOL <i>Brassica oleracea</i>
A0A078HME9_BRANA <i>Brassica napus</i> ,	A0A8S9IIZ9_BRACR <i>Brassica cretica</i>
A0A2G2WAZ7_CAPBA <i>Capsicum baccatum</i> ,	A0A6P6SN94_COFAR <i>Coffea Arabica</i>
A0A445AVH3_ARAHY <i>Arachis hypogaea</i> ,	A0A445END8_ARAHY <i>Arachis hypogaea</i>
F6HYL3_VITVI <i>Vitis vinifera</i>	A0A5N6RVV2_9ROSI <i>Carpinus fangiana</i>
A0A6J1KHL7_CUCMA <i>Cucurbita maxima</i> ,	A0A6J1E061_MOMCH <i>Momordica charantia</i>
A0A0A0LH38_CUCSA <i>Cucumis sativus</i> ,	A0A1S3BU26_CUCME <i>Cucumis melo</i>
A0A8T3B2K3_DENNO <i>Dendrobium nobile</i> ,	A0A3B6RRH2_WHEAT <i>Triticum aestivum</i>
A0A8I6Z6W4_HORVV <i>Hordeum vulgare</i> ,	A0A3L6DFV0_MAIZE <i>Zea mays</i>
A0A921U2C4_SORBI <i>Sorghum bicolor</i> ,	A0A3L6PDV3_PANMI <i>Panicum miliaceum</i>
A0A2S3HHG5_9POAL <i>Panicum hallii</i> ,	A0A2T7D VW7_9POAL <i>Panicum hallii</i>
A0A6G1CRT5_9ORYZ <i>Oryza meyeriana</i> ,	A0A8J5SZQ4_ZIZPA <i>Zizania palustris</i>

Figure 1 MSA of mitochondrial RNAPs (NEP) from various plant sources

3.2 'Mix and Match' MSA analysis of Plant Mitochondrial and Chloroplast NEPs

Figure 2 shows the 'mix and match' MSA of the plant mitochondrial and chloroplast NEPs. The N-terminal regions do not show much conservation, up to ~150 amino acids. Even though both show many consecutive Ss in the N-terminal regions, but the chloroplast N-terminal region shows a large number of consecutive Ss up to 9 of them and in addition to that, it also has a -DxD- type metal-binding motif (highlighted in green). BLASTp analysis of both the NEPs of *Arabidopsis thaliana* was performed. The mitochondrial NEP of *Arabidopsis thaliana* shows 59.05% identity to the chloroplast NEP, suggesting the NEPs of mitochondria and chloroplasts are distinctly different, but showed complete conservation of their catalytic regions (Fig. 2). Even though these NEPs are classified as T3/T7 RNA polymerase type, but they showed very little identity (the mitochondrial NEP of *Arabidopsis thaliana* showed only 28.24% identity to the T7 RNAP) suggesting a drastic divergence during evolution, but maintaining the catalytic cores still intact. The decapeptides in the NTD regions are highly conserved in both NEPs and highlighted. It is interesting to note that the metal-binding motifs, -HQD-, -HDS- and -DvD-, and the catalytic core regions, viz. -QVDRKLVKQTVMTSVYGVTY- are completely conserved in both the NEPs and highlighted. The CTD contains an invariant tetrad, -YFFN- motif (marked in red) in both the NEPs suggesting a possible common role.

3.1.2 CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) 'Mix and Match' MSA analysis of mitochondrial and chloroplast NEPs

Figure 2 'Mix and Match' MSA analysis of the NEPs of mitochondria and chloroplasts from various plant sources

Figure 3 shows the organization of the NEPs of the mitochondria and chloroplast of *A. thaliana*. The NTDs are not conserved in both the cases, whereas the other three domains are highly conserved and organized in the same order.

Figure 3 Domain-organization of the NEPs of mitochondria and chloroplasts (Numberings from the *A. thaliana* sequence)

3.3 Analysis of Active Site Amino Acids of the NEP from Plant Mitochondria

3.1.3 Active Site Amino Acids of the RNA Polymerase Catalytic Core

The catalytic core region essentially contains three components in DNA/RNA polymerases, viz. a template-binding pair –YG–, a basic catalytic amino acid –K/R– and a nucleotide discriminating amino acid –R–, placed at -4 to -5 from the catalytic K/R. These three highly conserved components of the catalytic core are found in the NEPs of the plant mitochondria also. Interestingly, the plant mitochondrial NEP's catalytic core, $^{-748}\text{DR}^{-4}\text{KLVK}^{753}\text{Q}^1\text{TVMTSVY}^8\text{GV}^{-}$, is identical to the catalytic core of the chloroplast NEP of *A. thaliana*, suggesting their common origin. Furthermore, the mitochondrial NEP's catalytic core regions are in close agreement with those already reported from other DNA/RNA polymerases (Table 2).

Table 2 Catalytic core regions of various RNA and DNA polymerases

Polymerase type	Catalytic core
SSU RNA/DNA pols	
Viral T7 SSU RNA pol	$^{-620}\text{WLA}^{\text{Y}^8}\text{GVTR}^{-4}\text{SVT}^{\text{K}^1}\text{R}^1\text{SVMTLA}^{\text{Y}^8}\text{GS}^{-}$
Viral SP6 SSU RNA Pol	$^{-612}\text{WDSI}^{\text{I}^8}\text{GITR}^{-4}\text{SLT}^{\text{K}^1}\text{K}^1\text{PVMTLPY}^8\text{GS}^{-}$
Mitochondrial SSU RNA pol (<i>Sc</i>)	$^{-1009}\text{TR}^{-4}\text{KVVKQ}^1\text{TVMTNVY}^8\text{GV}^{-}$
Mitochondrial SSU RNA pol (<i>H. sapiens</i>)	$^{-986}\text{TR}^{-4}\text{KVVKQ}^1\text{TVMTVY}^8\text{GV}^{-}$
<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I (SSU)	$^{-753}\text{QR}^{-4}\text{RSAK}^{754}\text{A}^1\text{INFGLIY}^8\text{GM}^{-}$
Chloroplast SSU DNA pol IA (<i>ARATH</i>)	$^{-873}\text{ER}^{-4}\text{RKAK}^{876}\text{M}^1\text{LNFSIAY}^8\text{GK}^{-}$
Chloroplast SSU DNA pol IB (<i>ARATH</i>)	$^{-857}\text{ER}^{-4}\text{RKAK}^{862}\text{M}^1\text{LNFSIAY}^8\text{GK}^{-}$
Chloroplast SSU RNA pol (NEP) (<i>ARATH</i>)	$^{-765}\text{DR}^{-4}\text{KLVK}^{770}\text{Q}^1\text{TVMTSVY}^8\text{GV}^{-}$
Mitochondrial SSU RNA pol (NEP) (<i>ARATH</i>)	$^{-748}\text{DR}^{-4}\text{KLVK}^{753}\text{Q}^1\text{TVMTSVY}^8\text{GV}^{-}$

Adapted from Palanivelu [5]; *Sc*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *ARATH*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*; The active site amino acids, highlighted in dark blue, are confirmed by SDM; and other techniques.

3.1.4 Polymerase Metal-Binding Sites

The second important site for the polymerase function is the catalytic metal-binding site which involves in the addition of the incoming nucleotides to the 3'-OH of the growing primer. The catalytic metal-binding amino acids of the mitochondrial NEP are arrived at sequence similarity. The two **Ds** in the –**HD**⁶⁷⁷– and –**HD**⁹⁰⁹S– motifs (highlighted in dark green in Figs. 1 and 2) are proposed as the catalytic metal-binding amino acids and they could bind a Mg²⁺ during catalysis. Interestingly, these two motifs are completely conserved in the NEPs of both mitochondria and chloroplasts from various plant sources (Fig. 2). The –**HD**⁸¹²S– motif is also found in T7 RNAP and its involvement was confirmed by an SDM experiment. It was found that the –**D**⁸¹²→N in the –**HDS**– motif exhibited no detectable activity [17]. The 2Ds, proposed in the metal-binding sites are also reported to be highly conserved among most of the SSU RNA polymerases. Usually the D in –**QD**– and the D in **HDS** are found to be involved in Mg²⁺-binding and 'NTP charge shielding'. They are widely reported in the SSU RNA polymerases like T3/T7 phage RNA polymerases and SSU RNA polymerases of plant and fungal mitochondria and plant chloroplasts [7]. Based on these data, Fig. 4 shows the proposed active site amino acids of the polymerase domain of the plant mitochondrial NEP. For a detailed description of the polymerase's mechanism, see Palanivelu [19].

3.1.5 PR Exonuclease Active Site

The PR exonuclease active site amino acids of NEPs from various plant mitochondria are arrived at from MSA analysis and their sequence similarities to other well-established DEDD-exonuclease superfamilies. The NEPs from various plant mitochondria belong to DEDD(H) subfamily as discussed below. The DEDD-superfamily of PR exonucleases uses either a Y or a H as the catalytic proton acceptor. An invariant H is found in the active site of mitochondrial NEPs (Table 3), and thus, this one belongs to the DEDD(H)-subfamily. Fijalkowska and Schaaper [20] have found DEDD(H)-subfamily of

PR exonuclease in the ε-subunits of the bacterial replicase multienzyme complexes (DNA pols III) which belongs to the DnaQ-H-family with the four active site carboxylates (D¹², E¹⁴, D¹⁰³, and D¹⁶⁷) with the invariant H¹⁶², which acts as the general base in catalysis. They also found that modification of the two conserved amino acid residues, viz. D¹²→Ala and E¹⁴→Ala, in the ε-subunit by SDM experiments, resulted in the loss of the exonuclease function. These observations were further corroborated by X-ray crystallographic analysis of the ε-subunit, ε-186, by Hamdan et al. [21]. An interesting DEDD-superfamily of PR 3'→5' exonuclease was found not in polymerases, but in the tRNA processing enzyme, RNase T. At least five amino acid residues, viz. D²³, E²⁵, D¹²⁵, H¹⁸¹ and D¹⁸⁶ were found on the active site of *E. coli* RNase T. The crystal structures of RNase T from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *E. coli* have been reported by Zuo et al. [22] and they found it also belongs to DEDD(H)-subfamily.

Tables 3 and 4 show the summary of the identified/confirmed DEDD(Y/H)-exonuclease active site amino acids in DNA/RNA polymerases from different viral, bacterial, fungal, plant and animal sources.

Table 3 DEDD-superfamily of PR exonuclease active site amino acids from viral, bacterial, fungal, plant and animal sources

Exo-Family	Consensus A-site Pattern	Proton Acceptor	Catalytic Metal ion*	ZBSs
DEDD(Y/H)-superfamily				
Prokaryotic PR Enzymes				
T4 DNA pol (<i>E. coli</i> Phage)	-D ¹¹² XE ¹¹⁴ -D ²¹⁹ -Y ³²⁰ -D ³²⁴ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol I (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ³⁵⁵ XE ³⁵⁷ -D ⁴²⁴ -Y ⁴⁹⁷ -D ⁵⁰¹ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol II (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ¹⁵⁶ XE ¹⁵⁸ -D ²²⁹ -Y ³³¹ -D ³³⁵ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
RNase D (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ²⁸ XE ³⁰ ---D ⁸⁵ ---Y ¹⁵¹ -D ¹⁵⁵ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol III, ε-subunit (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ¹² XE ¹⁴ -D ¹⁰³ -H ¹⁶² -D ¹⁶⁷ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
RNase T (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ²³ XE ²⁵ -D ¹²⁵ -H ¹⁸¹ -D ¹⁸⁶ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
PR Enzymes in Eukaryotic DNA Replicases				
DNA pol ε cat. subunit (<i>Sc</i>)	-D ²⁹⁰ VE ²⁹² -D ³⁸³ -Y ⁴⁷³ -D ⁴⁷⁷ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol δ cat. subunit (<i>Hs</i>)	-D ³¹⁶ IE ³¹⁸ ---D ⁴⁰² -Y ⁵¹¹ -D ⁵¹⁵ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
PR Enzymes in DNA Polymerases 1A and 1B from Plant Chloroplasts				
DNA polymerase 1A (<i>ARATH</i>)	-DTE ²⁹⁶ -----D ³⁶⁸ -----Y ⁴⁷⁰ ---D ⁴⁷⁴ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA polymerase 1B (<i>ARATH</i>)	-DTE ²⁷² -----D ³⁴⁶ -----Y ⁴⁴⁸ ---D ⁴⁵² -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
PR Enzymes in RNA Polymerase, NEP from Plant Chloroplasts				
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	-DVE ⁵⁵⁰ -----D ⁵⁷² -----H ⁵⁸⁶ ---D ⁵⁹⁰ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	-DVE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	-DVE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	-DIE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	-DTE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	-DTE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Carpinus fangiana</i>	-DTE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
PR Enzymes in RNA Polymerase, NEP from Plant Mitochondria				
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	-DIE ⁵³³ -----D ⁵⁵⁵ -----H ⁵⁶⁹ ---D ⁵⁷³ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Brassica napus</i>	-DVE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Coffea Arabica</i>	-DTE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	-DTE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Zea mays</i>	-DTE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Oryza meyeriana</i>	-DTE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1

Adapted from Palanivelu [5]. A-site, Active site; *Water-bound Zn²⁺; ZBSs, Number of zinc-binding sites; Active site amino acids, confirmed by SDM are highlighted in dark blue and X-ray crystallography, in light blue. *Sc*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *Hs*, *Homo sapiens*; *ARATH*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*.

Table 4 DEDD(Y/H)-superfamily exonuclease active site amino acids and their distance conservation

DEDD-Superfamily of PR Exonucleases (-DxE-E-H*/Y*---D*-)	
Phage DNA Polymerases	
T4 DNA pol (<i>E. coli</i> Phage)	-D ¹¹⁴ IE-----FD ²¹⁹ -----SY ³²⁰ N→3 aa←D ³²⁴ VE- [23]
T7 DNA pol (<i>E. coli</i> Phage)	-DIE ⁷ -----FD ²³⁵ -----DY ¹⁷⁰ N→3 aa←D ¹⁷⁴ VV-
Prokaryotic DNA Replicase (DNA pol III- ε-subunits)	
<i>E. coli</i>	-D ¹² TE-----FD ¹⁰² -----LH ¹⁶² G→4 aa←D ¹⁶⁷ AQ-
<i>Citrobacter amalonaticus</i>	-D ¹⁵ TE-----FD ¹⁰⁵ -----LH ¹⁶⁵ G→4 aa←D ¹⁷⁰ AQ
<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	-D ¹² TE-----FD ¹⁰² -----LH ¹⁶² G→4 aa←D ¹⁶⁷ AQ
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	-D ¹² TE-----FD ¹⁰² -----LH ¹⁶² G→4 aa←D ¹⁶⁷ AQ
Eukaryotic DNA Replicases	
DNA pol ε cat. subunit (<i>Sc</i>)	-D ²⁹⁰ IE-----FD ³⁸³ -----EY ⁴⁷³ S→3 aa←D ⁴⁷⁷ AV- [24,25]
DNA pol δ cat. subunit (<i>Hs</i>)	-D ³¹⁶ IE-----FD ⁴⁰² -----VY ⁵¹¹ C→3 aa←D ⁵¹⁵ AY- [26]
Plant DNA Polymerases IA (Plant Chloroplasts)[#]	
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	-D ²⁹⁴ TE-----FD ³⁶⁸ S-----SY ⁴⁷⁰ S→3 aa→D ⁴⁷⁴ AI-
<i>Chlorella desiccata</i>	-D ²⁹⁴ TE-----FD ³⁹⁴ R-----SY ⁴⁹³ S→3 aa→D ⁴⁹⁹ AK-
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	-D ⁴⁴⁷ TE-----FD ⁵²¹ S-----FY ⁶³⁴ S→3 aa→D ⁶³⁸ SI-
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	-D ²⁸⁴ TE-----FD ³⁵⁸ S-----SY ⁴⁶⁰ S→3 aa→D ⁴⁶⁴ AI-
Plant DNA Polymerases IB (Plant Chloroplasts)[#]	
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	-D ²⁷² TE-----FD ³⁴⁶ N-----SY ⁴⁴⁸ S→3 aa→D ⁴⁵² SI-
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	-D ³⁰⁰ TE-----FD ⁴⁰⁰ N-----CY ⁵⁷² S→3 aa→D ⁵⁷⁰ SI-
<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	-D ³⁴⁰ TE-----FD ⁴⁴⁵ N-----SY ⁵⁰² S→3 aa→D ⁵⁰⁰ SI-
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	-D ²⁵⁸ TE-----FD ³³² N-----SY ⁴³⁴ S→3 aa→D ⁴³⁸ SI-
<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I Exo [#]	-D ³⁵⁵ TE-----YD ⁴²⁴ -----RY ⁴⁹⁷ A→3 aa→D ⁵⁰¹ AD-
SARS-CoVs[^]	
SARS-CoV-1 ExoN/ACE2	- ⁹⁰ DVE-----D ²⁴³ -----AH ²⁶⁸ V→4 aa← ²⁷³ DAI-
MERS-CoV ExoN/DPP4	- ⁹⁰ DVE-----D ²⁴³ -----AH ²⁶⁸ V→4 aa← ²⁷³ DAI-
SARS-CoV-2 ExoN//ACE2	- ⁹⁰ DVE-----D ²⁴³ -----AH ²⁶⁸ V→4 aa← ²⁷³ DAI-
Nuclear-Encoded RNA Polymerase (NEP) from Plant Chloroplasts[^]	
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	-D ⁵⁴⁸ VE-----LD ⁵⁷² F-----NH ⁵⁸⁶ L→3 aa→D ⁵⁹⁰ LC-
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	-D ⁵⁷⁵ VE-----VD ⁵⁹⁹ F-----NH ⁶¹³ L→3 aa→D ⁶¹⁷ LC-
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	-D ⁵³⁸ VE-----LD ⁵⁶² F-----NH ⁵⁷⁶ L→3 aa→D ⁵⁸⁰ LC-
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	-D ⁵⁸⁶ VE-----LD ⁶¹⁰ F-----NH ⁶²⁴ L→3 aa→D ⁶²⁸ LC-
Nuclear-Encoded RNA Polymerase (NEP) from Plant Mitochondria[^]	
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	-DIE ⁵¹¹ -----VD ⁵⁹⁵ F-----NH ⁶⁰⁰ L→3 aa→D ⁵⁷³ LC-
<i>Brassica napus</i>	-DVE ⁵⁰⁰ -----LD ⁵⁵² F-----NH ⁶⁰⁰ L→3 aa→D ⁵⁷⁰ LC-
<i>Coffea Arabica</i>	-DTE ⁵⁰⁰ -----LD ⁵⁰⁸ F-----NH ⁶²² L→3 aa→D ⁶²⁰ LC-
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	-DTE ⁵⁰⁰ -----LD ⁵²⁸ F-----SH ⁵⁴² L→3 aa→D ⁵⁴⁶ LC-
<i>Zea mays</i>	-DTE ⁵⁰⁰ -----LD ⁵³¹ F-----SH ⁵⁴⁵ L→3 aa→D ⁵⁴⁰ LC-
<i>Oryza meyeriana</i>	-DTE ³⁰⁷ -----LD ³⁸⁹ F-----SH ⁴⁰³ L→3 aa→D ⁴⁰⁷ LC-

Adapted from Palanivelu [5]. *Sc*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *Hs*, *Homo sapiens* *The distance between the proton acceptor (H/Y) and the last D are 3 to 4 amino acids Active site amino acids confirmed by SDM analysis are highlighted in dark blue and by X-ray are highlighted in light blue #Similar active site amino acids are found in *E. coli* DNA pol I ^Interestingly, similar active site amino acids are found in SARS-CoVs and other human CoVs ACE2, Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2; DPP4, Dipeptidyl peptidase 4.

Figure 4 shows the proposed polymerase and PR exonuclease active sites. In the NEP of mitochondria, the active site H^{569} accepts the proton from the metal-bound water molecule to initiate catalysis, which is followed by the formation of a highly reactive Zn-hydroxyl free radical, resulting in the removal of a misincorporated nucleotide. Thus, the 3'→5' exonuclease↔polymerase activities switch between excision and incorporation modes without dissociation of the enzyme-substrate complex [27]. For a detailed mechanism of polymerase, see Palanivelu [19].

Mitochondrial NEP (*ARATH*) (PR exo) –RCD⁵³¹IE⁵³³-----NVD⁵⁵⁵F-----NH⁵⁶⁹L—SD⁵⁷³LC-

Figure 4 Proposed amino acids at the active sites of the polymerase and PR exonuclease of the NEP of plant mitochondria (Numberings from the *A. thaliana*'s sequence).

4 Conclusion

Mitochondria are semi-autonomous organelles and are found in all eukaryotic cells. They are partly controlled by their own genome and mostly by the nuclear imports. The nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase (NEP) is imported from the nucleus to the mitochondria and is involved in the transcription of all mitochondrial genes. The mitochondrial NEP showed only 59.05% identity to the NEP of chloroplasts from *Arabidopsis thaliana*, suggesting that the NEPs of mitochondria and chloroplasts are distinctly different. However, in both the NEPs, the polymerase catalytic core and PR exonuclease domains are completely conserved. The PR exonuclease of the mitochondrial NEP belongs to the DEDD-superfamily.

Compliance with ethical standards

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